

Potential Biologically Active Agents. XII. Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of Substituted *p*-Methylamino-benzenesulfonamides

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4-aminobenzenesulfonamides have been condensed with benzoxazolin-2-one, benzoxazolin-2-thione, benzothiazolin-2-thione, benzimidazole, benzotriazole and phthalimide under the conditions of the Mannich reaction. The compounds thus obtained have been tested for their antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Bacillus megaterium*.

THE efficacy of sulfa drugs as chemotherapeutic agents is well established. A good antimicrobial activity of benzazoles^{1,2} and phthalimides³ prompted us to prepare sulfanilamide derivatives of type I.

where R = H; 2-pyrimidyl; 4,6-dimethyl-2-pyrimidyl; 2,4-dimethyl-6-pyrimidyl and 1-phenyl-5-pyrazolyl and R₁ = 3-benzoxazolin-2-onyl; 3-benzoxazolin-2-thionyl; 3-benzthiazolin-2-thionyl; 1-benzimidazolyl; 1-benzotriazolyl and phthalimido.

Benzazoles and phthalimide were prepared by published procedures⁴⁻⁹ and transformed to the corresponding N-hydroxymethyl derivatives by the treatment with formalin¹⁰. Condensation of N-hydroxymethylbenzazoles with sulfa drugs afforded the desired compounds (I). In cases where the yields of the products were lower, a slightly different procedure was adopted to accomplish a better yield. The purity of the synthesised compounds was checked by t.l.c and i.r. spectra.

Infrared spectra were recorded in a Perkin Elmer 137 Spectrophotometer in KBr. The >C=O frequency was obtained at 1730-1770 cm⁻¹, NH at 3230 to 3289 cm⁻¹ and C=N at 1585 to 1627 cm⁻¹.

Experimental

Synthesis of *p*-(3-Benzazolylmethylamino)-benzenesulfonamides(I)

Method 1: In a typical procedure, 1.65 g. (0.01 mole) of N-hydroxymethylbenzoxazolin-2-one and 1.72 g. (0.01 mole) of 4-aminobenzenesulfonamide were heated under reflux in 25 ml of ethanol for 45 min. The contents were cooled and refrigerated for several days. The solid product thus separated was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol or dilute ethanol.

Method 2: A mixture of benzimidazole (1.18 g; 0.01 mole), 40% formalin (1 ml), sulfa pyrimidine (2.50 g; 0.01 mole) and ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed for 30 min. The product thus obtained was isolated and recrystallised from ethanol or dilute ethanol.

The compounds prepared by methods 1 and 2 are listed in Table 1.

Antibacterial Activity

The antibacterial activity of the compounds listed in Table 1 was determined by agar diffusion technique¹¹, using concentration of 10 mg/ml of the product. The test organisms included *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Bacillus megaterium*. In this study five compounds (6,7,10,11,16) inhibited the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* while eight compounds (1,2,4,8,10,11,15,16) inhibited the growth of *Salmonella typhi*. Inhibition of the growth of *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus megaterium* was observed only by compounds 6 and 11 respectively. Bacterial cultures maintained at C.D.R.I., Lucknow were used.

TABLE I—SUBSTITUTED *p*-METHYLAMINO BENZENESULFONAMIDES (I)

S. No.	R	m. p. ^a °C	Yield %	Molecular Formula	% N-analyses		Method used
					Found	Reqd.	
1-5 ; R ₁ = 3-Benzoxazolin-2-onyl							
1.	H	250	50	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₄ S	12.95	13.15	2
2.	4, 6-dimethyl- 2-pyrimidyl	134-35	69	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ S	16.72	16.46	1
3.	2-pyrimidyl	191-92	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄ S	17.31	17.60	1
4.	2, 4-dimethyl 6-pyrimidyl	244	60	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ S	16.49	16.46	1
5.	1-phenyl-5-pyrazolyl	214	40	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₄ S	15.43	15.17	2
6-9 ; R ₁ = 3-Benzoxazolin-2-thionyl							
6.	H	215	55	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	12.67	12.53	1
7.	4, 6-dimethyl- 2-pyrimidyl	135	60	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	15.62	15.86	1
8.	2-pyrimidyl	250	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	17.30 C, 51.80 H, 4.12	16.93 52.28 3.65	2
9.	2, 4-dimethyl- 6-pyrimidyl	215-17	55	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	15.97	15.86	1
10-13, R ₁ = 3-Benzothiazolin-2-thionyl							
10.	H	166	60	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	12.26	11.95	2
11.	4, 6-dimethyl- 2-pyrimidyl	128	40	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	15.65	15.30	1
12.	2-pyrimidyl	192	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	16.74	16.30	1
13.	2, 4-dimethyl- 6-pyrimidyl	210	50	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂	15.01	15.30	1
14, 15 ; R ₁ = 1-Benzimidazolyl							
14.	4, 6-dimethyl- 2-pyrimidyl	245	40	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	20.22	20.57	2
15.	2, 4-dimethyl-6- pyrimidyl	182	50	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	20.32	20.57	2
16, 17 ; R ₁ = 1-Benzotriazolyl							
16.	2, 4-dimethyl -6-pyrimidyl	234	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₂ S	24.03	23.94	2
17.	4, 6-dimethyl- 2-pyrimidyl	135	65	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₂ S	23.78	23.94	2
18 ; R ₁ = Phthalimido							
18	2-pyrimidyl	182	65	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₄ S	17.39	17.10	2

^a, Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are not corrected.

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